

THE APPLICATION OF INTERFACE ELEMENTS AND VISCO-PLASTICITY TO MICRO MECHANICAL ANALYSES OF FRACTURE IN COMPOSITES

J.C.J. SCHELLEKENS^{1,*}, R. DE BORST^{1,2} AND S. WEIHE³

¹ Delft University of Technology, Department of Civil Engineering
P.O. Box 5048, 2600 GA Delft, The Netherlands

² TNO Building and Construction Research

³ University of Stuttgart, Institute for Statics and Dynamics of Aerospace Structures

ABSTRACT

Micromechanical analyses are presented of matrix fracture and fibre-matrix debonding in carbon-epoxy composites. The fibres and the matrix are connected by special interface elements which allow for a geometric discontinuity (debonding) to arise. The fibres and the matrix of the composite structure are modelled as a visco-plastic continuum. In the micro-mechanical analyses of matrix fracture it is demonstrated that, upon mesh-refinement, the load deflection curves converge to a unique solution, and that the width of the localisation band remains finite. When the interaction between matrix cracking and debonding is investigated the same observations hold.

Keywords: Micromechanics, interface elements, visco-plasticity.

1. INTRODUCTION

The structural performance of fibre-reinforced materials depends to a major extent upon the interfacial bonding between fibres and matrix material. Debonding often marks the onset of matrix cracking and may play a crucial role in the locations at which matrix cracking is initiated. At further stages of the loading process we observe joining of matrix cracks as well as of matrix cracks and debonded fibre-matrix interfaces until complete loss of structural integrity finally occurs.

To obtain qualitative information on the progress of debonding and the influence of the interfacial bond properties on the structural performance of the composite material micromechanical analyses can be carried out. In numerical micromechanical analyses the fibres as well as the matrix are modelled by continuum elements and the interface is represented by special interface elements (Ngo and Scordelis 1967, Goodman *et al.* 1968, Schäfer 1975, Beer 1985, Rots 1988, Schellekens 1992, Schellekens and de Borst 1993a). In the undamaged state (fully bond) a sufficiently high dummy stiffness ensures that no additional deformation occur in the interface, which is assumed to have a zero stiffness. After the tensile strength, or another equivalent strength measure, has been exceeded, the originally fully intact area gradually evolves into a geometric discontinuity, i.e. an internal stress-free boundary (at full debonding). In the formulation chosen here the strength/stiffness degradation occurs gradually. During the debonding process energy is dissipated. The quintessence of the approach for debonding is that the amount of dissipated energy is assumed to be equal to the fracture toughness G_c of the interface that fractures. This model ensures a correct energy dissipation during debonding, so that below a certain discretisation, the crack propagation is independent of the fineness of the mesh. At the same time, the model results in a correct treatment of size effects (Schellekens 1992, Schellekens and de Borst 1993b).

The strength degradation in the matrix is modelled using a strain-softening Von Mises plasticity

* Currently on leave at the Institute for Statics and Dynamics of Aerospace Structures, University of Stuttgart, Stuttgart, Germany.

model. An inherent difficulty of any strain-softening model when utilised in a standard, rate-independent continuum setting is that under quasi-static loading conditions the field equations cease to be elliptic. Well-posedness of the rate boundary value problem is lost and the mathematical model is no longer a proper description of the physics. In finite element simulations this loss of well-posedness becomes apparent through an extreme mesh sensitivity. Near failure all deformation concentrates in the smallest possible zone that can be resolved by the grid. Upon mesh refinement the failure zone collapses into a discrete plane (localisation) and the energy consumption during the failure process tends to zero. When the failure zone is known in advance interface elements as also used for the fibre-matrix interface can be located at the expected crack path. Together with a specification of the fracture energy that is dissipated in the crack a mesh-insensitive numerical solution can then be obtained.

If the crack path is not known in advance, two solutions are possible. Firstly, one can adaptively remesh during the non-linear process such that the correct crack path is aligned with the element boundaries (Larsson 1990). Secondly, and this approach is followed here, enriched or rate-dependent continuum models can be adopted (commonly named regularisation strategies). In this contribution a visco-plastic continuum is used to regularise the strain-softening Von Mises plasticity model (Needleman 1988, Loret and Prevost 1990, Sluys 1992). This approach intrinsically introduces an internal length scale in the continuum and have the effect that the rate boundary value problem remains well-posed also after the onset of strain-softening for the matrix material. Accordingly, physically meaningful numerical solutions can be obtained.

The paper is organised as follows. Firstly, the interface elements and the constitutive model for the debonding process are described. Then, a typical example is analysed, whereby attention is given to issues like the sensitivity of the solution to mesh refinement and the interaction between debonding and matrix cracking. For a description of the Duvaut-Lions visco-plasticity model that is utilised in this contribution the reader is referred to (Loret and Prevost 1990, Sluys 1992).

2. NUMERICAL MODELLING OF THE FIBRE-MATRIX INTERFACE

The fibres and the matrix of the composite are connected by special interface elements (see Figure 1). Because of space limitations we will only briefly discuss the formulation of the interface elements and the associated constitutive model. For a more elaborate description the reader is referred to Schellekens (1992), and Schellekens and De Borst (1993a).

Figure 1. Line interface elements

In interface elements tractions \mathbf{t} and relative displacements \mathbf{v} between upper and lower interface side are evaluated. When the interface is still elastic the traction-relative displacement relation reads:

$$\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{D}_I^{el} \mathbf{v} \quad (1)$$

where the matrix \mathbf{D}_I^{el} is given by:

$$\mathbf{D}_I^{el} = \begin{bmatrix} d_n & 0 \\ 0 & d_t \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

In the nonlinear regime, that is, when debonding initiates, the behaviour of the interface is

described by an orthotropic hardening/softening plasticity model. In this study we assume that the yield condition for interface plasticity is given by

$$\Phi^{pl}(\mathbf{t}, \kappa) = C_{nn}t_n^2 + C_{tt}t_t^2 + C_n t_n - \bar{t}^2(\kappa) = 0 \quad (3)$$

with C_{ii} and C_n a set of material constants, \bar{t} a normalised yield traction and κ the hardening/softening parameter. t_n and t_t are the components of the traction vector.

If \bar{t}_n^c and \bar{t}_t^c denote the compressive and tensile yield tractions in the direction normal to the interface side and if \bar{t}_s is the shear yield traction we obtain:

$$C_{nn} = \frac{\bar{t}^2}{\bar{t}_n^t \bar{t}_n^c} \quad C_{tt} = \frac{\bar{t}^2}{\bar{t}_t^2} \quad C_n = \frac{\bar{t}^2}{\bar{t}_n} - \frac{\bar{t}^2}{\bar{t}_n^c} . \quad (4)$$

Recasting eq. (3) in matrix-vector notation yields

$$\Phi^{pl}(\mathbf{t}, \kappa) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{t}^T \mathbf{P} \mathbf{t} + \mathbf{t}^T \mathbf{p} - \bar{t}^2(\kappa) = 0 \quad (5)$$

in which $\mathbf{t}^T = (t_n, t_t)$, $\mathbf{P} = \text{diag}(2C_{nn}, 2C_{tt})$ and $\mathbf{p}^T = (C_n, 0)$.

As soon as this condition is satisfied, the total relative displacement rate $\dot{\mathbf{v}}$ is decomposed into an "elastic" part, $\dot{\mathbf{v}}^{el}$, and a "plastic" part, $\dot{\mathbf{v}}^{pl}$, as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}} = \dot{\mathbf{v}}^{el} + \dot{\mathbf{v}}^{pl} \quad (6)$$

The elastic relative displacement rate is related to the traction rate by

$$\dot{\mathbf{t}} = \mathbf{D}_I^t \dot{\mathbf{v}}^{el} , \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{D}_I^t is a properly linearised tangent modulus. The assumption of an associated flow rule yields for the plastic relative displacement rate:

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}}^{pl} = \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial \Phi^{pl}}{\partial \mathbf{t}} . \quad (8)$$

For the present orthotropic yield criterion (5) this gives:

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}}^{pl} = \dot{\lambda} (\mathbf{P} \mathbf{t} + \mathbf{p}) . \quad (9)$$

Furthermore, the scalar κ in the case of a work hardening/softening hypothesis reads

$$\kappa = \int \dot{\kappa} dt \quad \text{with} \quad \dot{\kappa} = \mathbf{t}^T \dot{\mathbf{v}}^{pl} . \quad (10)$$

2.1 Description of the Model

Due to the fact that we intend to model both plasticity and cracking in the interface we can no longer regard the inelastic deformations (\mathbf{v}^{pl}) as being purely plastic. Therefore, we define the inelastic relative displacements as crack relative displacements (\mathbf{v}^{cr}) except for the mode-I inelastic relative displacements that are induced by a compressive loading. These are considered as plastic (see Figure 2). The degradation of the elastic properties of the interface is coupled with the inelastic relative displacement due to cracking (\mathbf{v}^{cr}). In this case the stiffness that determines the tractions in unloading or reloading is the so-called secant stiffness matrix denoted by \mathbf{D}_I^s . From the moment of crack-closure (defined by $v_n \leq v_n^{pl}$), that is in the compressive loading regime, the initial elastic stiffness governs the interface behaviour. It is assumed that due to the irreversible plastic relative displacements that may occur, the traction relative displacement diagram shifts horizontally over a distance v_n^{pl} (see Figure 2). Furthermore the assumption is made that the degradation of the equivalent yield traction \bar{t} is not influenced by yielding in compression. Thus the amount of inelastic work that is used to determine the values of \bar{t} and C_n is defined as $\kappa = \int \mathbf{t}^T \dot{\mathbf{v}}^{cr} dt$. In the analyses that are presented in the next section a linear relation between κ and \bar{t} has been assumed: $\bar{t} = \bar{t}_0(1 - \kappa/G_c)$, where \bar{t}_0 denotes the initial transverse tensile strength of the interface and G_c denotes the fracture toughness of the interface. A physical interpretation of work-softening model is that once the fracture toughness of the interface has been released as free-surface energy, the strength and stiffness of the interface will have completely reduced to zero.

Figure 2. Traction relative displacement relation for the mode-I component

3. MICRO MECHANICAL ANALYSES OF COMPOSITE FRACTURE

Since a poor bonding between fibres and matrix limits the possibilities of composites that contain high performance fibres, at present much effort is put in understanding the interaction between fibres and matrix and improving the interface bonding. In this section we shall present the results micro-mechanical analysis of matrix fracture and the interaction between matrix fracture and fibre-matrix debonding. In the analyses the matrix is modelled as a visco-plastic continuum and special interface elements are used to provide the bond between the fibres and the matrix. For the matrix a linear relation between the equivalent yield stress ($\bar{\sigma}$) and the equivalent plastic strain ($\bar{\epsilon}$) is assumed ($\bar{\sigma} = \bar{\sigma}_0(1 - \bar{\epsilon}/\bar{\epsilon}_u)$).

We start with the investigation of matrix fracture in a carbon-epoxy composite. In the composite we assume a periodic arrangement of the fibres which results in a natural choice for the reference volume element (RVE). The uni-directional composite (50% fibre volume fraction) is loaded in transverse tension as shown in Figure 3. The material properties for the Apollo IM 43-750 carbon fibres and the Ciba-Geigy Araldite Epoxy matrix are listed in Table 1. Also the material properties for the interface elements, which enter the model at a later stage, are included in Table 1.

Figure 3. Geometry and properties of the composite ply

Table 1. Material properties

	Fibres	Matrix	Interface Elements	
E [N/mm ²]	12000	3200	d_n, d_t [N/mm ³]	100.0
ν	0.3	0.37	$\bar{t}_0 = \bar{t}_n$ [N/mm ²]	85.0
$\bar{\sigma}_0$ [N/mm ²]	-	85.0	$\bar{t}_n = \bar{t}_t$ [N/mm ²]	85.0
$\bar{\epsilon}_u$ [mm/mm]	-	0.45	G_c [J/m ²]	100.0

Due to symmetry only a quarter of the RVE was discretised using 170(mesh1), 336(mesh2) and 1348(mesh3) quadratic plane-strain triangles respectively, as is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Finite element discretisations of a RVE

Figure 5. Load displacement curves for the right boundary. Effects of variation of η and $\bar{\epsilon}_u$.

Figure 6. Load displacement curves for the right boundary. Effects of strain rate on the RVE response.

Figure 7. Contour plots of equivalent plastic strains at a displacement of $0.2 \mu\text{m}$.
 Left diagrams: $\dot{\epsilon}_{11}$ 0.0031 mm/mm. Right diagrams: $\dot{\epsilon}_{11}$ 0.00156 mm/mm.
 $\eta = 1.0$, $\bar{\epsilon}_u = 0.1$.

In the vertical direction free contraction of the RVE is allowed whereas an equal displacement constraint was imposed on the nodes of the right boundary. The response of the three meshes was calculated taking different values for the relaxation time η , the ultimate equivalent plastic strain $\bar{\epsilon}_u$ and for the loading rate $\dot{\epsilon}_{11}$. The results of the mesh-refinement study are presented in Figures 5 and 6 in terms of load-displacement curves for the right boundary of the RVE. We observe that the response of the RVE converges to a unique solution upon mesh refinement. This is result of the regularising effect of the visco-plastic continuum model. Furthermore Figures 5 and 6 show that for decreasing loading rates and for the lower value of the relaxation time the difference in response of the three discretisations slightly increases. This is explainable since for the limit cases of $\dot{\epsilon}_{11} \rightarrow 0$ and $\eta \rightarrow 0$ respectively, the standard (mesh-sensitive) continuum solution is obtained. Figure 7 presents contour plots of the equivalent plastic strains for the different meshes at a displacement of $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ of the right boundary. It is shown that the width of the localisation band remains finite and approximately constant upon mesh-refinement. Although a slight decrease in width is observed for the right diagrams which correspond to the lower loading rate.

In the next series of analyses the attention is focused on the interaction between fibre-matrix debonding and matrix fracture. At this point the interface elements are introduced in the finite element model. The three meshes of Figure 4 have been analysed again with the material data set specified in Table 1. Figure 8 shows the load displacement curves for the three discretisations. It is observed that when fibre-matrix debonding is taken into account the results also converge to the same solution. As a reference the results for perfect bonding have been included in Figure 7 and it can be seen that the influence of the fibre-matrix bond strength on the response of the RVE is significant.

Figure 8. Load displacement curves for the right boundary. Influence of fibre matrix debonding on the RVE-response

Finally, the contour plots of the equivalent plastic strains (Figure 9, meshes 1 and 3) demonstrate that size of the localisation zone is not affected by the mesh refinement. Hence mesh-insensitive results have been obtained for the analysis of the interaction between matrix fracture and debonding.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The calculations presented in this paper have been carried out using the DIANA finite element package of TNO Building and Construction Research (TNO-BOUW).

Figure 9. Contour plots of equivalent plastic strains at a displacement of $0.2 \mu\text{m}$. Strain rate 0.0031 mm/mm . $\eta = 1.0$, $\bar{\epsilon}_u = 0.1$.

REFERENCES

- Beer, G. (1985) - An Isoparametric Joint/Interface Element for Finite Element Analysis, *Int. J. Num. Meth. Engng.*, **21**, pp. 585-600.
- Goodman, R.E., Taylor, R.L. and Brekke, T.L. (1968) - A Model for the Mechanics of Jointed Rock, *ASCE J. Soil Mech. Found. Div.*, **94**, pp. 637-659.
- Larsson, R. (1990) - *Numerical Simulation of Plastic Localisation*, Publication 90:5, Department of Structural Mechanics, Chalmers University of Technology, Göteborg.
- Loret, B. and Prevost, J.H. (1990) - Dynamic Strain Localization in Elasto-(Visco-)Plastic Solids, Part 1. General Formulation and One Dimensional Examples, *Comp. Meth. Appl. Mech. Engng.*, **83**, pp. 247-273.
- Needleman, A. (1988) - Material Rate Dependence and Mesh-Sensitivity of Localisation Problems, *Comp. Meth. Appl. Mech. Engng.*, **67**, pp. 69-86.
- Ngo, D., and Scordelis, A.C. (1967) - Finite Element Analysis of Reinforced Concrete Beams, *J. Amer. Concrete Institute*, **64**, pp. 152-163.
- Rots, J.G. (1988) - *Computational Modelling of Concrete Fracture*, Dissertation, Delft University of Technology, Delft.
- Schäfer, H. (1975) - A Contribution to the Solution of Contact Problems With the Aid of Bond Elements, *Comp. Meth. Appl. Mech. Engng.*, **6**, pp. 335-354.
- Schellekens J.C.J. (1992) - *Computational Strategies for Composite Structures*, Dissertation, Delft University of Technology, Delft.
- Schellekens, J.C.J. and de Borst, R. (1993a) - On the Integration of Interface Elements, *Int. J. Num. Meth. Engng.*, **36**, pp. 43-66.
- Schellekens, J.C.J. and de Borst, R. (1993b) - A Non-Linear Finite Element Approach for the Analysis of Mode-I Free Edge Delamination in Composites, *Int. J. Solids Structures*, **30(9)**, pp. 1239-1253.
- Sluys, L.J. (1992) - *Wave Propagation, Localisation and Dispersion in Strain Softening Solids*, Dissertation, Delft University of Technology, Delft.